

PACIFICUS

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“SHINE @ 30”

Isolated, sheltered from the dreary world beyond.
The little pearls settled for the secluded journey along.
Thirty years gone and went, oh pearls cherish the wonderful years they've spent.
Shinning so brightly, serene and sparkling, not worried about the tragedy of the future.

Shinning, shinning, shinning, until the world went into hiding.
Wondering if they'll ever see the light and shine once more.
In isolation the pearls are kept, whilst the world is swept by the storm.
Patient the little pearls, filled with serenity in the place where they're safe.
The ability to shine while being alone, is it even possible?

Devoid of the world, the pearls will have none.
There has to be a way, for the third decade had just begun.
They'll find their way to shine in between this dark situation.

Making their new year positive despite the devastation
Throughout the hardships, struggles and misfortune,
Pearl's are wise, using their fruitfulness to make the most out of their distortion.

Despite all the trouble they went through, Pearl's are remarkable.
Learning and growing truly unstoppable.
Things have become more complicated,
It's difficult to keep up, but Pearl's get up.

What new problem they face won't stop them
for Pearl's will strive.
And as they strive, they will shine.
Shining more than ever, with integrity and might.

They can turn this around, no longer surrounded by darkness,
As we create a new world of brightness
Pearl's this year see a whole new light
They shine through this isolation; they sparkle in this situation.

This is a challenge that we have made our strength,
Pearl's go through great lengths,
In order to shine.

